

Evaluation report of esports Program in Tecnológico de Monterrey

Criteria Definitions

- **Improving Cognitive Skills:** This criterion evaluates the development and application of complex cognitive strategies, including problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making abilities.
- **Effective Knowledge Acquisition:** This criterion measures the extent to which students acquire, retain, and apply knowledge in practical contexts.
- **Engagement and Motivation:** This criterion assesses the level of student participation, interest, and commitment to the activities within the eSports program.
- **Development of Digital Competences:** This criterion evaluates proficiency in using digital tools and platforms, essential for navigating and excelling in a technologically driven environment.

Rubric' Objective

The objective of this evaluation rubric is to assess the eSports program's impact on the learning experiences and skill development of GT students. This rubric aims to measure the extent to which the program enhances cognitive skills, facilitates effective knowledge acquisition, boosts engagement and motivation, and develops digital competences. The goal is to ensure that the eSports program supports the holistic development of gifted students, preparing them for complex problem-solving and innovation in academic and real-world contexts.

Rubric Table

Criteria	Level 1 (Basic)	Level 2 (Intermediate)	Level 3 (Advanced)	Score
	0 - 11	12 - 24	25 - 35	
Improving Cognitive Skills	Limited development of cognitive skills, with minimal application of complex strategies.	Moderate development of cognitive skills, applying some complex strategies in specific situations.	Advanced development of cognitive skills, effectively and consistently applying complex strategies in various situations.	28
	0 - 9	10 - 19	20 - 30	24

Effective Knowledge Acquisition	Basic knowledge acquisition with poor retention and application in practical contexts.	Intermediate knowledge acquisition with occasional retention and application in practical contexts.	Advanced knowledge acquisition with high retention and effective, consistent application in various practical contexts.	
	0 - 6	7 - 13	14 - 20	
Engagement and Motivation	Limited participation and motivation, with low involvement in program activities.	Moderate participation and motivation, showing interest and commitment in some program activities.	High participation and motivation, with significant involvement and commitment in all program activities.	18
	0 - 4	5 - 9	10 - 15	
Development of Digital Competences	Limited development of digital competences, with minimal proficiency in using digital tools and platforms.	Moderate development of digital competences, with proficiency in using some digital tools and platforms.	Advanced development of digital competences, with high proficiency in using various digital tools and platforms effectively.	12
	Total:			

Justification:

Improving cognitive skills (Score: 28 / 35)

The program significantly enhances cognitive skills through rigorous training sessions, strategy meetings, and video reviews. These activities promote advanced problem-solving, critical thinking, and strategic planning, which are important for the cognitive development of GT students. The consistent application of complex strategies in various gaming scenarios reflects high cognitive engagement and intellectual stimulation, essential for maximizing the potential of gifted students.

Effective knowledge acquisition (Score: 24 / 30)

Students acquire extensive knowledge through theoretical classes and practical applications, ensuring a deep understanding of game mechanics and strategies. The program's structure facilitates the retention and application of this knowledge in competitive settings, aligning well with the educational needs of gifted students who thrive on in-depth, comprehensive learning experiences. However, there is room for improvement in ensuring that all students consistently achieve this high level of knowledge acquisition.

Engagement and motivation (Score: 18 / 20)

The high level of student participation and motivation is evident in regular training sessions, competitive engagements and involvement in additional activities such as volunteering and social events. Gifted

students often need stimulating and engaging environments to maintain their interest and motivation. The program successfully creates such an environment, fostering the ongoing commitment and enthusiasm that are necessary for the continued development of gifted learners.

Development of digital competences (Score: 12 / 15)

The program effectively develops digital competences through the use of high-performance gaming equipment and various digital platforms for training and performance assessment. These competencies are at the heart of navigating the digital landscape, a skillset for gifted learners in the modern world. While the program performs adequately in this area, further enhancement of digital literacy and competence could raise the overall competence of students.

Highlights

- The program's comprehensive approach promotes both cognitive and social skill development, contributing positively to students' overall growth.
- Detailed rubrics and an online platform for performance assessment ensure continuous improvement and effective tracking of progress.
- High levels of participation and motivation among students reflect the program's ability to foster a supportive and dynamic environment.

Improvement needs:

- Address the challenges in attracting professional-level talent by enhancing recruitment strategies and providing more incentives (e.g., scholarships, food support).
- Increase the budget for a specialized team to allow for comprehensive planning and execution, ensuring a higher quality program.
- Implement flexible scheduling and academic support tailored for athletes to better balance their academic and training commitments.